

THE PROCESS OF STUDENTS' ADAPTATION TO SCHOOL AND THE CONCEPT OF PSYCHOLOGICAL SUPPORT

Son of Yusufzhanov Anaskhan Ikram Namdu Faculty of Pedagogy and Psychology

Student of pedagogy and psychology, group 404

Abstract

The subject of pedagogical activity is the organization of educational activities aimed at mastering the socio-cultural experience of students as the basis and condition of development. This article talks about the process of students' adaptation to school and the concept of psychological support.

Key words: pedagogical activity, adaptation, experience, development, professional activity, pedagogical skills;

Enter

The result of pedagogical activity is the student's personal, intellectual development, improvement, formation as a person, as a subject of educational activity. It is a high art in the implementation of pedagogical activities based on demonstrated knowledge, personal qualities and pedagogical experience. High demands are placed on the teacher's moral qualities. He should have human moral qualities, be a good organizer. Systematic ideological and moral self-improvement of the teacher gives high social meaning to his organizational ability and talent. It is impossible for a teacher to effectively organize the pedagogical process without human attraction, goodwill and mutual sympathy between the teacher and the children. Therefore, high morals, spiritual integrity and faith, knowledge and intellectual development, human attractiveness are the most important conditions for the formation of the pedagogical influence of the educator, the head of the class.

Research methodology

A high level of professional self-awareness is one of the most important components that form the ability of a modern pedagogical specialist to achieve success in professional activities, professional self-awareness. Pedagogical excellence is mastered by the teacher's

best examples, standards and pedagogical activity, pedagogical communication, professional behavior, which ensures high results in learning, education and development of students. A teacher can perform his professional activity at different skill levels. Pedagogical excellence is manifested in the teacher's mastery of the best examples, standards, levels of activity, pedagogical communication and professional behavior. Skills affect the results of training, education and development of school students. Teachers with high teaching skills have a deep knowledge of science and its teaching methods, have a broad scientific and cultural outlook, are familiar with child psychology, and skillfully use teaching methods. They know how to organize the group and individual work of students, gather the class, they have a trusting relationship with children. Teachers of average level of teaching skills know science, master the methodology, have a broad cultural and scientific outlook. However, their pedagogical skills (constructive, communicative, organizational) are not sufficiently developed, such teachers have average abilities, love children, but do not always understand and know their individual psychological characteristics. The idea of the pedagogical process is a look at the nature of the pedagogical work associated with its own characteristics, the real perspective is trying to create a new educational system promoted by the pedagogy, which arose as a result of a different understanding of the work of the teacher-educator. Different psychological processes occur in children of school age and students who are first admitted to school. We will analyze some of them.

Hearing ability. For the first time, the child should hear normal calm speech, in other words, he should have constant attention. When we teach a child to repeat the same thing several times, sometimes out loud, we ourselves create such a situation. Why can't you hear me? Parents get angry when the child does not respond to their words and requests. Unfortunately, I can say with complete confidence that this is often a mirror image of the parent's position. Mother, mother, okay, mother, mother-ah! - the more often you hear this at your address, the more difficult it will be for the child to learn to hear normal speech rather than shouting. How to help? You can agree with the child and hold a one-day competition with "hear it for the first time", setting the score and mandatory discussion of the results. When the child makes a request or just turns to you, say out loud: "I heard you."

Analysis and results

"We wrote, we wrote, our fingers are tired" - this is not just a children's rhyme, this is the reality of first graders and a teacher's headache. Children need to work a lot with their fine motor skills. As usual, it's not easy. Especially considering that modern children who are used to remote controls, touchpads and keyboards have great difficulties in training their fingers, the most interesting way to develop fingers is building blocks with a lot of small details. Teach the student to draw pictures on coloring pages in different directions without turning the picture: from top to bottom, from left to right, from top to bottom. Then your child will not have difficulties in writing in the first grade. Learn letters instead of developing interest. Parents need to know that curiosity is achieved through movement, that is, permission to touch, grasp, disassemble, crush, tear, build and break. And it's called "exploring the world", not "breaking things". The age at which interest appears is one and a half years. You will learn to interpret the most diverse moments of life. The general awareness of the first grader is very important. It is also useful for developing logic, attention, and memory.

Conclusions

Teach children to write instead of developing fine motor skills. It is impossible to teach a preschool child to write letters and numbers, because he gets used to holding the pencil incorrectly, uses a different writing technique, and then it is difficult to learn it again at school.

References

1. Vahidov M., Psychology of preschool education, T., 1970;
2. Davletshin M., Criminology and its diagnostics, T., 1979,
3. Tokareva V., Psychology of moral development of student personality, T., 1989; 4. Ghaziyeh E., Psychology science XXI year, T., 2002;
5. Ghaziyev E., Psychology, T., 2003;